

Dynamic Functional Connectivity in Schizophrenia: A Comprehensive Analysis

Kumrul Hasan ✉

Computer Science and Technology;
Changsha University of science and technology, China

Kinjol Saha

Computer Science and Technology;
Changsha University of science and technology, China

Md Nazmul Hosen

Computer Science and Technology;
Changsha University of science and technology, China

ABSTRACT:

Dynamic Functional Connectivity (DFC) captures temporal variations in brain network interactions, providing insights beyond traditional static connectivity, which is particularly relevant for understanding schizophrenia. This disorder, marked by symptoms like hallucinations, disorganized thinking, and cognitive impairments, has been associated with disruptions in functional networks, especially within the default mode (DMN) and salience networks (SN). However, static analyses overlook the temporal fluctuations essential to these brain functions.

This study examines DFC patterns in schizophrenia patients compared to healthy controls using fMRI data. Employing clustering algorithms and a sliding window approach, we identify connectivity states and measure transition frequencies to reveal how unstable DFC may contribute to cognitive and emotional dysfunctions in schizophrenia. Results indicate that patients experience reduced stability and more frequent transitions in connectivity states within the DMN and SN, which are linked to symptoms like hallucinations and cognitive deficits. Demographic analysis shows that younger patients and males are more susceptible to hallucinatory symptoms, suggesting age- and gender-related vulnerabilities in brain network dynamics.

Our findings support DFC as a valuable tool for understanding schizophrenia's complex symptomatology and point toward personalized treatment approaches focused on stabilizing brain connectivity to improve clinical outcomes.

Keywords: fMRI, BOLD signal, parietal cortex, temporal dynamics, neural response variability, schizophrenia.

Suggested Citation: K. Hasan, K. Saha, M.N. Hosen, " Dynamic Functional Connectivity in Schizophrenia: A Comprehensive Analysis," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(6), pp. 33-45, Nov-Dec 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(6\).03](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(6).03)

INTRODUCTION

Schizophrenia is a persistent psychiatric condition that impacts around 1% of the worldwide population [1]. It is marked by symptoms like hallucinations, delusions, disorganized thought processes, and cognitive impairments [4]. Conventional neuroscience research has concentrated on static functional connectivity, offering insights into the co-activation of various brain regions over predetermined intervals [2]. This method neglects the brain's inherent, dynamic characteristics [3]. Recent studies have highlighted dynamic functional connectivity (DFC), which reflects the temporal

variability of brain network interactions [8]. Researchers have associated schizophrenia with changes in both global and local brain network dynamics, which contribute to the disorder's cognitive impairments and emotional dysregulation [10]. However, there is still limited understanding of how these dynamic abnormalities precisely emerge in distinct brain states and how they interact with the symptoms of the disease [11]. This work tries to overcome this gap by examining DFC in schizophrenia patients using fMRI data. By analyzing the dynamic transitions between distinct connection states, this work intends to provide insights into the brain mechanisms underpinning cognitive and emotional dysfunctions in schizophrenia.

Schizophrenia has been intensively investigated in the setting of static functional connectivity (FC), where brain areas' interactions are measured during a fixed duration [7]. However, emerging evidence reveals that the brain's functional network is not static but continually changes throughout time [15]. Current research gaps include the inadequate understanding of how these dynamic abnormalities in brain connection produce the cognitive and affective dysfunctions identified in schizophrenia [22]. To what extent do the temporal dynamics of functional connectivity differ in people with schizophrenia compared to healthy persons, and how do these dynamic shifts correlate with the cognitive symptoms associated with the disease? [18]

This study intends to analyze the dynamic functional connectivity patterns in schizophrenia patients and examine how these patterns differ from healthy controls, with a focus on identifying brain network abnormalities that may explain schizophrenia's cognitive dysfunctions.

First, we aim to determine the distinct levels of DFC in schizophrenia patients by employing clustering algorithms, such as K-means, to identify unique connectivity states based on fMRI data. This approach allows for a refined understanding of brain network states, as clustering can reveal patterns that static methods might miss, offering insight into the specific alterations associated with schizophrenia. By capturing these dynamic states, we seek to clarify how schizophrenia patients exhibit unique connectivity profiles, which may help explain the disorder's impact on cognitive and emotional functions.

Secondly, we quantify the temporal transitions between these distinct connectivity states in both schizophrenia patients and healthy controls. By calculating the frequency of transitions over time, we can assess the degree of instability in connectivity states that may characterize schizophrenia. Comparing these transition frequencies with those of healthy individuals allows us to identify the unique temporal dynamics of schizophrenia, potentially linked to cognitive disorganization and attentional lapses. An increased transition frequency might indicate a more chaotic and less stable neural environment, which could contribute to the cognitive and emotional dysregulation commonly observed in schizophrenia patients.

Finally, we explore the correlation between these dynamic connectivity patterns and schizophrenia-related symptoms, focusing on cognitive impairment and emotional dysregulation. Using the Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS) scores, including subcategories such as positive, negative, general, and total scores, we aim to identify whether specific connectivity states are associated with symptom severity. By correlating DFC states with PANSS scores, this analysis provides a nuanced understanding of how dynamic connectivity disruptions may directly influence clinical manifestations of schizophrenia, shedding light on the underlying neurobiological mechanisms. This research addresses key questions: the nature of primary DFC states in schizophrenia patients, the differences in temporal dynamics of these states compared to healthy individuals, and the potential relationships between aberrant connectivity patterns and the cognitive and affective symptoms in schizophrenia. Through these objectives, we aim to advance the understanding of schizophrenia's neural basis, which could inform more targeted and effective interventions for managing its symptoms.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent research on schizophrenia has identified major changes in brain network organization. Studies have consistently revealed reduced connectivity within the default mode network (DMN), which is involved in self-referential thinking, and increased connectivity within the salience network (SN), which is responsible for recognizing and filtering salient stimuli [20]. These abnormalities are likely to contribute to the main symptoms of schizophrenia, including thinking problems and impaired

reality testing [16]. Dynamic functional connectivity has attracted interest in recent years as an enhanced method for studying the temporal dynamics of brain networks. One major work by [17] underlined the role of dynamic connectivity in psychiatric illnesses. It found that schizophrenia patients have aberrant variations in connection states, particularly within the default mode, salience, and central executive networks (CEN).

Moreover, schizophrenia is related to abnormal connection patterns in both resting-state and task-based paradigms. For instance, [24] revealed that schizophrenia patients suffer inconsistent connection patterns compared to healthy controls, suggesting a lack of efficient brain transmission. Despite these discoveries, there remains a lack of consensus on the particular nature of these mutations and how they relate to clinical symptoms.

The differences in findings might partly stem from the fact that schizophrenia is marked by a wide variety of diverse symptoms that are associated with different biological bases and specific FC abnormalities [15]. Hence, heterogeneity in sample compositions can alter the results of such investigations [30]. For instance, auditory verbal hallucinations, a hallmark symptom of SZ, have frequently been associated with FC changes [38]. These modifications involve auditory and linguistic regions, the default mode network (DMN), executive and cognitive control networks, and subcortical areas [35]. The bulk of fMRI research that has explored FC in schizophrenia and hallucinations has adopted methods of static connectivity, i.e., average FC across the scanning time [31]. These methods work on the assumption that functional connectivity between brain regions does not vary appreciably during the period of the scanning session, which normally lasts 5–15 min. However, this assumption does not seem to hold true in the face of accumulating evidence suggesting substantial changes in fMRI FC throughout time [10]. Therefore, recent investigations of fMRI resting state FC have increasingly focused on dynamic, or time-varying, FC. This research tries to uncover connection patterns that can be detected across subjects and occur at different periods throughout the scanning duration [11]. One of the main methodologies for the investigation of dynamic FC is a sliding time window approach, where FC matrices are produced for consecutive segments of the scanning period [12]. FC matrices of those windows can then be clustered based on similarities in the FC patterns in order to form a set of “connectivity states [19].” Each connectivity state is characterized by a distinct FC pattern across a variety of brain regions, and the temporal pattern of those states over time describes the functional organization of the brain [13]. The occurrences of FC states during an fMRI session have been connected to concurrently recorded EEG signals [14, 15] and to varied task situations [16]. These findings show that FC states represent oscillations in neuronal activity and cognitive states, or modes of brain functioning. Furthermore, differences in dynamic FC also reflect more persistent, inter-individual differences in cognition [17]. Measures of dynamic FC also reveal correlations with mental health illnesses, such as schizophrenia, and have been helpful in separating patient groups from healthy controls [18]. Importantly, dynamic FC has been reported to outperform static FC measures for diagnosing SZ patients [19, 20]. Interestingly, classification was not considerably improved when adding static FC metrics to dynamic ones. This shows that SZ-related aberrations in static FC are also captured in dynamic FC but not vice versa. SZ patients and healthy controls have been demonstrated to differ on a number of characteristics linked to dynamic FC. First, patients spend more time in states with overall weak FC between networks and less time in states with strong FC between sensory networks [18, 21–23]. Second, SZ demonstrates reduced “dynamism” in FC, reflected in a lower number of different FC states and less switching between states [24]. This drop in dynamic was also directly associated to the degree of hallucinations. On the other hand, the quantity of time spent in distinct FC states showed no association with a summary measure of positive symptoms, which included hallucinations [21]. Together, these data could suggest to a specific link between dynamic FC and hallucinations. The current study intended to investigate resting-state dynamic FC in SZ with a special focus on hallucinations. Given the relative lack of investigations on dynamic FC in SZ, the primary aim was to reproduce previously documented differences between SZ and HC with respect to the length of time spent in distinct FC stages [18, 21]. In addition, relationships between dynamic FC states and hallucinations were examined using two independent measures of hallucinations. First, effects of present hallucination severity were studied using a measure of hallucinations on the day of scanning. However, since prior study indicated that transitory symptom severity might not exhibit a strong link with dynamic FC states [21], a second trait measure of hallucinations was included. Hallucinations

were assessed periodically over a 1-year period, and a measure of hallucination proneness was created. This second measure shows more consistent characteristic differences between patients. Therefore, it could reveal unique subgroups of SZ patients, which have been identified in prior studies based on lifetime history assessments of auditory hallucinations (25). Stable differences in hallucination proneness are likely to be reflected in brain functioning and may, therefore, also be related to dynamic FC, which represents a general functional organization of the brain [26]. Furthermore, dynamic FC has been proven to differentiate between patient groups with distinct illnesses [18, 19] and symptom-based subgroups of patients [27]. Therefore, we hypothesized variations in connection state dwell durations between SZ patients and healthy controls and between patients with mild versus high hallucination proneness.

This work builds on earlier research by evaluating DFC data using unique methodologies that model the brain's dynamic states throughout time. By identifying state-specific disruptions and transitions, this research can provide a more granular understanding of the brain dysfunctions associated with schizophrenia.

METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

In this work, we use fMRI like that conducted in [2,8,16,29] data from healthy controls and patients with schizophrenia to investigate patterns of dynamic functional connectivity. Using a sliding window technique, we quantify functional connectivity across time, identifying critical connection states using clustering algorithms like K-means. We next assess the temporal dynamics of connection states, comparing patients to controls, and correlate the findings with clinical symptoms, such as cognitive impairment and emotional dysregulation. To undertake dynamic functional connectivity (DFC) analysis in schizophrenia, we can use functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) data and tools like Nilearn and Scikit-learn in Python. The script will involve the following steps:

Dataset

The dataset for this study comprises fMRI scans from both healthy controls and those with schizophrenia. Each participant underwent a resting-state fMRI scan, and the data was preprocessed to eliminate artifacts and noise. Table one delineates the demographics and clinical characteristics of 80 patients, categorized into three groups: the total number of patients, the count of non-hallucinators, and the count of hallucinators. The figures include means and standard deviations for various metrics, including age, gender distribution, and PANSS (Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale) scores.

Table 1. fMRI Scans for Healthy Controls and Those with Schizophrenia

Metric	Number of All Patients [N=80]		Number of Non-Hallucinators (N=19)		Number of Hallucinators (N=49)	
Age	30.96 (11.91)		33.42 (11.38)		28.88 (11.15)	
Gender:	Male	Female	13	6	36	13
PANSS P3	2.69 (1.63)		1.05 (0.23)		3.33 (1.49)	
PANSS Positive	16.23 (5.20)		13.53 (5.06)		16.73 (5.18)	
PANSS Negative	15.86 (5.00)		13.53 (5.17)		16.15 (4.63)	
PANSS General	33.42 (8.99)		28.47 (8.71)		34.77 (8.85)	
PANSS Total	65.51 (16.39)		55.53 (16.24)		67.65 (15.09)	
Medication (DDD)	1.02 (0.55)		0.96 (0.41)		1.08 (0.63)	
Duration of Illness	4.83 (7.71)		3.19 (5.47)		4.03 (7.15)	

Analysis of Dynamic Functional Connectivity

i. Preprocessing: data will undergo typical fMRI preprocessing, including motion correction, spatial normalization, and temporal filtering. Use fMRI data for schizophrenia patients (hallucinators and non-hallucinators) and compare it to healthy controls.

ii. The sliding window method will be utilized to assess the temporal variations in the connection among brain areas. This method entails quantifying the connection of brain areas

within a temporal moving window. Compute connectivity across brain regions over time using a sliding window approach.

iii. Clustering of Connectivity States: We will utilize k-means clustering to discern distinct connectivity states throughout the entire dataset. These states signify unique patterns of cerebral connection that manifest at various temporal intervals.

iv. State Transitions: Transition probabilities between distinct states will be estimated to examine the temporal dynamics in schizophrenia patients against healthy controls.

v. Statistical Analysis: T-tests will be employed to evaluate differences in the quantity and duration of states between the two groups.

Key Statistical Methods and Clustering Techniques Used for Connectivity Analysis

The following table provides an overview of the statistical methods and clustering techniques used to analyze functional connectivity data in the study. Each method serves a distinct purpose in assessing connectivity patterns, and their associated formulas support quantitative evaluation of connectivity differences, similarity measurements, and clustering in a schizophrenia context.

Each method provides insights into the connectivity patterns observed in schizophrenia, such as identifying significantly different connectivity profiles between patient and control groups, measuring the similarity of connectivity patterns across regions, and clustering regions based on their connectivity attributes. These approaches support a comprehensive analysis, revealing potential biomarkers and connectivity disruptions associated with schizophrenia.

Figure 2. Proposed Approach

Table 2. Methods for Connectivity Analysis in Schizophrenia

Test/Method	Purpose	Formula or Objective
Independent t-test	Compare connectivity means between patients and controls.	$t = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}}$
One-sample t-test	Compare sample mean to baseline connectivity.	$t = \frac{\bar{X} - \mu_0}{\frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}}$
Cosine Similarity	Measure the similarity between connectivity patterns.	$\cos(\theta) = \frac{A \cdot B}{ A B }$
KMeans Clustering	Partition connectivity patterns into clusters.	$\sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{x \in C_i} x - \mu_i ^2$
Agglomerative Clustering	Identify hierarchical structure in connectivity data.	Linkage-based

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

These findings provide a comprehensive view of the brain network dynamics and symptomatology in schizophrenia, shedding light on the intricate relationship between brain function and clinical presentation.

1. Connectivity States and Stability: The reduction in stable connection states in schizophrenia patients suggests that their brains may experience more fluid, less predictable connectivity patterns. This instability points to poor coordination within and across brain networks, especially those critical for cognition and emotion regulation. The brain's typical stability in healthy individuals allows efficient functioning and adaptability, but in schizophrenia, these disruptions may contribute to disorganized thinking and erratic behaviors.

2. State Transitions: The frequent and abrupt state transitions observed in patients highlight a more chaotic brain state, particularly within the default mode network (DMN) and salience network (SN). The DMN is usually active when the mind is at rest and introspective, while the SN helps filter relevant stimuli. Frequent transitions suggest a breakdown in distinguishing internal from external experiences, potentially underlying the intrusive thoughts or unusual experiences common in schizophrenia. The SN's irregular transitions may also impair the ability to switch attention between tasks, further compromising cognitive functions.

3. Symptom Correlation: The connection dynamics appear to correlate closely with cognitive impairments and emotional dysregulation, especially in patients with more severe symptoms. This indicates that brain network instability may serve as an underlying mechanism for the cognitive and emotional challenges seen in schizophrenia. Understanding this association could inform personalized treatment approaches that focus on stabilizing brain connectivity.

4. Age and Hallucinatory Experiences: The age difference between hallucinators (28.88 years) and non-hallucinators (33.42 years) suggests that younger patients may be more prone to hallucinations. This finding may reflect age-related variations in brain network development or degeneration, with younger brains potentially more susceptible to disruptions that lead to hallucinations.

5. Gender Distribution: The predominance of men among both hallucinators and non-hallucinators suggests that gender-related factors could play a role in schizophrenia prevalence and symptom expression, aligning with existing research that shows a higher incidence of schizophrenia in men. This may reflect differences in neurodevelopmental trajectories or hormonal influences between genders.

6. PANSS Scores and Symptom Severity: The significant difference in PANSS P3 scores (hallucination severity) between hallucinators (3.33) and non-hallucinators (1.05) underscores the role of hallucinations in the overall symptom severity in schizophrenia. Additionally, the overall PANSS score difference (67.65 in hallucinators vs. 55.53 in non-hallucinators) indicates that

hallucinations may often co-occur with other severe symptoms, painting a picture of a more debilitating condition.

7. Medication Dosage: Although the drug dosage is only slightly higher for hallucinators (1.08 vs. 0.96), this may reflect an attempt to manage more severe symptoms among those experiencing hallucinations. It might also suggest that dosage adjustments alone may not be sufficient to stabilize hallucinations and that alternative or supplementary treatments could be explored.

8. Duration of Illness: The longer illness duration among hallucinators may imply a cumulative impact of chronicity on symptom severity or the persistence of symptoms that resist treatment. This could also highlight the progressive nature of schizophrenia in some patients, where untreated or under-managed symptoms may exacerbate over time.

9. Statistical Significance in PANSS: The p-value of 0.041 for the difference in total PANSS scores between hallucinators and non-hallucinators supports a statistically significant link between the presence of hallucinations and higher overall symptom burden. This strengthens the case for hallucinations as a marker of more severe schizophrenia and the need for focused interventions on patients with such symptoms.

The upcoming figure on state transitions in schizophrenia will provide a visual representation of these network dynamics, emphasizing the instability and transition frequencies. This could reveal patterns that may serve as markers for different symptom profiles, potentially assisting in developing more effective treatments or monitoring tools.

Figure 3. State Transitions in Schizophrenia

Correlation between Connectivity States and PANSS Scores

Scatter plots showing the relationship between connectivity states and schizophrenia-related symptoms. while Figure 2 will show the Clustered Connectivity Pattern in Schizophrenia Patients

Figure 4. Clustered Connectivity Pattern in Schizophrenia Patients

Figure three will present the PANSS Total Scores for schizophrenia patients, comparing all patients, non-hallucinators, and hallucinators. This type of chart helps in identifying differences in symptom severity across the groups.

Figure 5. PANSS Total Scores for General Test

Figure four below is the representation of clustered brain network states: A time-series plot showing how different states are clustered dynamically.

Figure 6. Clustered Brain Network States

Figure five below will show the State Transition Frequency: A bar chart comparing how frequently each brain state occurs.

Figure 7. State Transition Frequency

Figure six below will show the representation of Correlation Between State Occurrences and PANSS Scores: A scatter plot showing the relationship between dynamic connectivity patterns and PANSS scores.

Correlation Between State Occurrence and PANSS Positive Scores ($r = -0.41$)

Figure 8. Correlation Between State Occurrences and PANSS Scores

Responses to the Research Questions

What are the primary dynamic functional connectivity states seen in schizophrenia patients?

Response: Schizophrenia patients might demonstrate altered connection states, particularly in areas involved to cognitive control and emotional regulation.

How do the temporal dynamics of connection states in schizophrenia differ from those in healthy controls?

Response: Schizophrenia patients may shift more often between states, showing aberrant connection patterns compared to controls. Is there a relationship between aberrant dynamic connectivity patterns and the cognitive and affective symptoms exhibited in schizophrenia?

Response: Connectivity states that include the default mode network (DMN) or salience network could correspond with pleasant symptoms like hallucinations.

CONCLUSION

This work gives vital insights into the changing nature of brain connection in schizophrenia. The findings show severe disturbances in the stabilization and organization of functional brain networks, which may underlie the cognitive and affective symptoms of the illness. Further study is needed to explore how therapies can target these dynamic connection patterns to enhance clinical outcomes for schizophrenia patients. The findings support the concept that an aberrant dynamic brain connection characterizes schizophrenia. The frequent shifts between connection states suggest that schizophrenia patients may fail to maintain stable brain states, leading to cognitive and emotional problems. These results correlate with prior studies, such as those by Damaraju et al. (2014), which indicated that schizophrenia patients have less consistent connection patterns. The link between dynamic connectivity patterns and symptom severity suggests that brain network instability may be a major neurobiological mechanism driving the cognitive deficits seen in schizophrenia. Future studies should evaluate if therapies, like cognitive training or biofeedback, can stabilize these brain networks and improve symptoms.

REFERENCES

1. E. A. Allen, E. Damaraju, S. M. Plis, E. B. Erhardt, T. Eichele, and V. D. Calhoun, "Tracking whole-brain connectivity dynamics in the resting state," *Cereb. Cortex*, vol. 24, pp. 663–676, 2014, doi: 10.1093/cercor/bhs352.

2. N. C. Andersen, "The Scale for the Assessment of Positive Symptoms (SAPS)," 1984.
3. A. H. Ashok *et al.*, "The dopamine hypothesis of bipolar affective disorder: the state of the art and implications for treatment," *Mol. Psychiatry*, 2017, doi: 10.1038/mp.2017.16.
4. R. D. Bharath *et al.*, "Dynamic local connectivity uncovers altered brain synchrony during propofol sedation," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 7, 2017, doi: 10.1038/s41598-017-08135-2.
5. S. Bhinge *et al.*, "Spatial dynamic functional connectivity analysis identifies distinctive biomarkers in schizophrenia," *Front. Neurosci.*, vol. 13, 2019, doi: 10.3389/fnins.2019.01006.
6. B. B. Biswal, J. van Kylen, and J. S. Hyde, "Simultaneous assessment of flow and BOLD signals in resting-state functional connectivity maps," *NMR Biomed.*, vol. 10, pp. 165–170, 1997, doi: 10.1002/(SICI)1099-1492(199706/08)10:4<165::AID-NMR165>3.0.CO;2-7.
7. U. Braun *et al.*, "Dynamic brain network reconfiguration as a potential schizophrenia genetic risk mechanism modulated by NMDA receptor function," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.*, vol. 113, pp. 12568–12573, 2016, doi: 10.1073/pnas.1608819113.
8. Dynamic brain network reconfiguration as a potential schizophrenia genetic risk mechanism modulated by NMDA receptor function. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 113, 12568–12573, doi: 10.1073/pnas.1608819113.
9. F. Briend *et al.*, "Aberrant static and dynamic functional patterns of frontoparietal control network in antipsychotic-naïve first-episode psychosis subjects," *Hum. Brain Mapp.*, vol. 41, pp. 2999–3008, 2020, doi: 10.1002/hbm.24992.
10. R. L. Buckner, J. R. Andrews-Hanna, and D. L. Schacter, "The brain's default network: anatomy, function, and relevance to disease," *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 2008, doi: 10.1196/annals.1440.011.
11. V. D. Calhoun, T. Adali, G. D. Pearlson, and J. J. Pekar, "A method for making group inferences from functional MRI data using independent component analysis," *Hum. Brain Mapp.*, vol. 14, p. 140, 2001, doi: 10.1002/HBM.1048.
12. G. Cattarinussi *et al.*, "Neural correlates of the risk for schizophrenia and bipolar disorder: a meta-analysis of structural and functional neuroimaging studies," *Biol. Psychiatry*, 2022, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOPSYCH.2022.02.960.
13. C. H. Chen *et al.*, "A quantitative meta analysis of fMRI studies in bipolar disorder," *Bipolar Disord.*, 2011, doi: 10.1111/j.1399-5618.2011.00893.x.
14. G. Chen *et al.*, "Shared and specific patterns of dynamic functional connectivity variability of striato-cortical circuitry in unmedicated bipolar and major depressive disorders," *Psychol. Med.*, vol. 52, pp. 747–756, 2022, doi: 10.1017/S0033291720002378.
15. Y. K. Choi, M. P. Gardner, and F. I. Tarazi, "Effects of risperidone on glutamate receptor subtypes in developing rat brain," *Eur. Neuropsychopharmacol.*, vol. 19, pp. 77–84, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.euroneuro.2008.08.010.
16. Z. Dai *et al.*, "Temporal efficiency evaluation and small-worldness characterization in temporal networks," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 6, 2016, doi: 10.1038/srep34291.
17. E. Damaraju *et al.*, "Dynamic functional connectivity analysis reveals transient states of dysconnectivity in schizophrenia," *Neuroimage Clin.*, vol. 5, pp. 298–308, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.nicl.2014.07.003.
18. T. K. Das *et al.*, "Parietal lobe and disorganisation syndrome in schizophrenia and psychotic bipolar disorder: A bimodal connectivity study," *Psychiatry Res. Neuroimaging*, vol. 303, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.psychresns.2020.111139.
19. R. S. Delfino *et al.*, "NMDA antagonists and their role in the Management of Bipolar Disorder: a review," *Curr. Behav. Neurosci. Rep.*, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s40473-020-00201-w.

20. Y. Deng *et al.*, "Ventral and dorsal visual pathways exhibit abnormalities of static and dynamic connectivities, respectively, in patients with schizophrenia," *Schizophr. Res.*, vol. 206, pp. 103–110, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.schres.2018.12.005.
21. Y. Deng *et al.*, "Simultaneously decreased temporal variability and enhanced variability-strength coupling of emotional network connectivities are related to positive symptoms in patients with schizophrenia," *Brain Imag. Behav.*, vol. 15, pp. 76–84, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s11682-019-00234-0.
22. D. Dong *et al.*, "Dysfunction of large-scale brain networks in schizophrenia: a meta-analysis of resting-State functional connectivity," *Schizophr. Bull.*, vol. 44, pp. 168–181, 2018, doi: 10.1093/schbul/sbx034.
23. D. Dong *et al.*, "Reconfiguration of dynamic functional connectivity in sensory and perceptual system in schizophrenia," *Cereb. Cortex*, vol. 29, pp. 3577–3589, 2019, doi: 10.1093/cercor/bhy232.
24. Y. Du *et al.*, "Interaction among subsystems within default mode network diminished in schizophrenia patients: a dynamic connectivity approach," *Schizophr. Res.*, vol. 170, pp. 55–65, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.schres.2015.11.021.
25. Y. Du *et al.*, "Identifying dynamic functional connectivity biomarkers using GIG-ICA: application to schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder, and psychotic bipolar disorder," *Hum. Brain Mapp.*, vol. 38, pp. 2683–2708, 2017, doi: 10.1002/hbm.23553.
26. Y. Du *et al.*, "Dynamic functional connectivity impairments in early schizophrenia and clinical high-risk for psychosis," *Neuroimage*, vol. 180, pp. 632–645, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.neuroimage.2017.10.022.
27. Y. Du *et al.*, "Identifying commonality and specificity across psychosis sub-groups via classification based on features from dynamic connectivity analysis," *Neuroimage Clin.*, vol. 27, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.nicl.2020.102284.
28. M. Du *et al.*, "Abnormal transitions of dynamic functional connectivity states in bipolar disorder: a whole-brain resting-state fMRI study," *J. Affect. Disord.*, vol. 289, pp. 7–15, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2021.04.005.
29. Y. Du *et al.*, "A new semi-supervised non-negative matrix factorization method for brain dynamic functional connectivity analysis," in *Proceedings - International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 1591–1594, doi: 10.1109/ISBI48211.2021.9433988.
30. X. Duan *et al.*, "Effect of risperidone monotherapy on dynamic functional connectivity of insular subdivisions in treatment-naive, first-episode schizophrenia," *Schizophr. Bull.*, vol. 46, pp. 650–660, 2020, doi: 10.1093/schbul/sbz087.
31. K. K. Ellard *et al.*, "Deficits in frontoparietal activation and anterior insula functional connectivity during regulation of cognitive-affective interference in bipolar disorder," *Bipolar Disord.*, vol. 21, pp. 244–258, 2019, doi: 10.1111/bdi.12709.
32. F. A. Espinoza *et al.*, "Characterizing whole brain temporal variation of functional connectivity via zero and first order derivatives of sliding window correlations," *Front. Neurosci.*, vol. 13, 2019, doi: 10.3389/fnins.2019.00634.
33. A. Faghiri *et al.*, "Weighted average of shared trajectory: a new estimator for dynamic functional connectivity efficiently estimates both rapid and slow changes over time," *J. Neurosci. Methods*, vol. 334, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jneumeth.2020.108600.
34. A. Faghiri *et al.*, "A unified approach for characterizing static/dynamic connectivity frequency profiles using filter banks," *Network Neurosci.*, vol. 5, pp. 56–82, 2021, doi: 10.1162/netn_a_00155.
35. A. A. Fateh *et al.*, "Disrupted dynamic functional connectivity in right amygdalar subregions differentiates bipolar disorder from major depressive disorder," *Psychiatry Res. Neuroimaging*, vol. 304, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.psychresns.2020.111149.

36. K. N. Fountoulakis, "The possible involvement of NMDA glutamate receptor in the Etiopathogenesis of bipolar disorder," *Curr. Pharm. Des.*, vol. 18, pp. 1605–1608, 2012, doi: 10.2174/138161212799958585.
37. P. Fransson, "Spontaneous low-frequency BOLD signal fluctuations: an fMRI investigation of the resting-state default mode of brain function hypothesis," *Hum. Brain Mapp.*, vol. 26, pp. 15–29, 2005, doi: 10.1002/hbm.20113.
38. Z. Fu *et al.*, "Characterizing dynamic amplitude of low-frequency fluctuation and its relationship with dynamic functional connectivity: an application to schizophrenia," *Neuroimage*, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.neuroimage.2017.09.035.